

Project Title **Implementing FAIR Workflows: a proof of concept study in the field of consciousness**

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D4.2 Communication Plan

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Executive Summary

The Implementing FAIR Workflows Project aims to leverage the existing persistent identifier infrastructure and research information management systems to build a proof of concept research workflow for neuroscience research that's FAIR by inception. The project will provide an example to enable and encourage the wider neuroscience community to adopt FAIR practices.

The goal of the communication effort within the project is to generate lasting engagement during and beyond the project lifetime, bring the researcher community onboard with the adoption of FAIR compliant workflows, and provide reliable resources for service providers to implement relevant functionalities to support the adoption after the completion of the project. This deliverable describes in detail the communications strategy, plan, tools, and success metrics to be used to achieve the goals of the project.

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Introduction

The Implementing FAIR Workflows project is a 3-year project, led by a core team of 2 organizations, involving 5 partners and 2 supporting organizations. The main goal of the project is to fully leverage the existing persistent identifier infrastructure and research management systems and develop a proof of concept research workflow for neuroscience research that's FAIR by inception, and provide an example to enable and encourage the wider neuroscience community to adopt these practices. Effective communication and engagement efforts are instrumental for the success of the project, which hinges on the trust, acceptance, and sustained impact of the project output on the neuroscience research community.

It is thus an important step of the project to develop and execute the communication plan, to effectively inform the various stakeholder groups of the project, and invite feedback from those interested in the progression and outputs of the project, as well as engage the wider researchers community.

This document describes the communication strategy, approach, stakeholder/ target audience, channels planned for the duration of the project, and outlines the evaluation metrics that will be used to benchmark the outcome of various communication efforts.

Communication strategy

The goal of communication, together with the dissemination efforts, is to generate lasting engagement during the project lifetime, bring the researcher community onboard with the adoption of such workflows, and provide reliable resources for service providers to implement relevant functionalities to support the adoption after the completion of the project. To achieve this, we will strategically employ various engagement methods to clearly convey the project team's vision and practical experience of the implementation of FAIR workflows; provide targeted information with enough detail, values, and persuasiveness, and actively pursue and be responsive to community feedback.

The key approach to communication in this project is to provide the right message to the relevant stakeholder group. Research workflow design, metadata harvesting and exchange between research information systems, and enabling usage tracking for research outputs are all crucial aspects of the project efforts and communication materials need to be crafted with the audience's interests and perspectives in mind when engaging with each of the distinct stakeholder groups.

We will invite researchers, service providers and integrators, funders, and the wider research data community to engage in the FAIR workflows efforts by building awareness and comprehension around the concept, showcasing the use cases, sharing the experiences and expertise, and demonstrating results and impact. A separate dissemination plan (Deliverable 4.1) will be developed to specifically address the work towards boosting adoption and amplifying community impact.

Strategic components

- Collaboration strategy within the core team
- Information flow among project partners within and across work packages
- Invited feedback from advisors and interested parties within and external to the project
- Communication of the project progression with the community and the public
- Amplify the impact of project outputs

Communication in work packages

The communication strategy is part of WP4, but in this project each work package has a communication component. WP1 defined the project midterm and final reporting commitments; WP2 requires close collaboration between project partners and demand efficient internal communication planning and execution; WP3 includes the development of communication materials targeting the researchers community to engage them in workflow adoption; while WP4 laid down specific timeframe for engagement with different stakeholder groups throughout the project period.

The information flow across the WPs is depicted in Figure 1. The workflows specifications developed in WP1 by DataCite and MPIEA will define the contributions from the project partners to be undertaken in WP2, and prepare for WP3 by providing use cases and user profiles for the dashboard development work; the implementation of the workflow and system integrations from WP2 will lay the data pipeline and be communicated back to the technical development team at DataCite for dashboard building, and generate plenty of technical and practical documentation to serve as the basis for WP4, in which description of integrations for service providers and adoption guidelines for researchers are developed; finally the values delivered by the dashboard will support the dissemination of the project outputs and incentivize adoption beyond the project lifetime.

Figure 1. Communication efforts across work packages

Stakeholders

The project continues the momentum built from precursor infrastructure projects like Horizon 2020’s ODIN/ THOR/ FREYA, Make Data Count, and on-going efforts like machine-actionable DMP and FAIRsFAIR, thus inherits much of the stakeholder groups that have been engaging with, as well as participating in the works around the implementation of FAIR principles and open science practices. The main stakeholder groups and representative members of the group are listed in Table 2.

Stakeholder Group	Members
Researchers	Neuroscience researchers across career stages Researchers from other disciplines

	Research project managers
Research producing organizations	Universities Libraries Research administrators Research funding organizations
Service providers	PID service providers Disciplinary data repositories Research registries Research reporting systems
Research data communities	Data aggregator Data curator RDA/ INCF
Concurrent FAIR projects	FAIRsFAIR FAIR Island
Interest groups	Metadata standardization working groups Standard bodies

Table 1. Project stakeholders

The stakeholder groups will be targeted strategically through the diverse channels employed in the project, to maximize the effectiveness of communication. Table 3 maps our top level stakeholder groups to the communication activities planned within the project, with the activities that have the most potential impact to the corresponding group marked with an “x”. The specific content types for the different formats of communication are elaborated in the Communication Channel section of this document.

	Social media	Webinars	Training materials	Conferences	Workshops
Researchers		x	x		x
Research producing organizations		x		x	x
Service providers		x		x	x
Research data communities	x			x	
Concurrent FAIR projects				x	

Interest groups	x	x	x		
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Table 2. Project stakeholder groups and target communication channels.

We also plan to leverage the distinct voices of the project partner organizations and members of the advisory committee in their respective communities to amplify the reach of the project communication efforts. We will work with them to identify opportunities to create synergies across channels, domains, and geographies.

Communication approach

Project branding

A logo is created to build an easily distinguishable identity for the project, and brand the communication materials and outputs. The logo is available in dark blue and white versions to fit usage on both light and dark backgrounds. Templates for project documents and slides featuring the logo are available for the project team and partners.

Figure 2. Project logo, dark blue logo on white background and white logo on dark blue background.

Communication channels

When deciding on channels used for effective communication, we put special emphasis on the sustainability of the project legacy, including the continued support for the technical infrastructure, and advocacy for the adoption of the FAIR workflows. To avoid obsolescence of project resources, we will integrate communication channels to existing communication platforms maintained by DataCite, and host project outputs on established and well-accepted community repositories, instead of establishing standalone online presence for the project.

Webpage

As the primary online presence and dissemination tool of the project, the project webpage is established at the beginning of the project timeline. The project page consists of an overview of the project proposal, including the motivation, objectives, partners and supporters of the project, and a description of each of the work packages.

The aim of the project webpage is to serve as the entry point for stakeholders and interested parties to quickly gain an understanding of the scope and purpose of the project, find relevant information that is linked from the project, and track the progress of the project.

The outputs of the deliverables will be linked to the page as the project proceeds. The updates of the webpage will be accompanied by tweets and community newsletters.

WHAT IS THE IMPLEMENTING FAIR WORKFLOWS PROJECT?

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Funder	Templeton World Charity Foundation
Project Directors	Dr. Helena Cousijn (DataCite), Prof. Lucia Melloni (MPIEA)
Project Organization	DataCite
Duration	36 Months (October 2021 - September 2024)

Implementing FAIR Workflows: A proof of concept study in the field of consciousness is a 3-year, multi-partner project funded by the TWCF, aimed at building and implementing an exemplar FAIR and Open research workflow based on die Realität of an entire research Lebenszyklus. The project will produce a practical and easy to use guide for other scientists to improve the FAIRness of their own research.

Project motivation

1. Papers only tell a small fraction of the story, hard to comprehensively evaluate a research study based on papers alone.
2. The complex experimental protocols and data in the field of neuroscience aggravate the reproducibility problems.
3. Open and FAIR research increase reproducibility and reuse, infrastructure and tools are available but adoption fragmented.
4. To motivate open practice adoption and FAIR compliance, researchers need concrete examples of FAIR workflows that are easy to implement.

Figure 3. Project webpage, hosted on the DataCite website.

Social mediaTwitter

The DataCite Twitter handle (13.6k follower) will be used for communicating project milestones, conference attendance, webinars and other communication activities, with the hashtag #fairworkflowsproject. Twitter has been proven to be one of the most effective channels for engaging with the targeted community and a unique platform to invite informal conversations and input from the interested parties. Through monitoring the tweet analytics, a built-in function of Twitter, we can collect data on the most active time period of the day for our target audience and plan our tweets accordingly. The impact of twitter messages will be monitored to improve the communication strategy, and reported as part of the project achievements.

Other than Twitter, we also plan to use LinkedIn. DataCite is active on LinkedIn and has a substantial follower group in the relevant fields, which overlap significantly with the stakeholder group of the project, similarly the DataCite blog and PIDForum will also be used to communicate the project outcome and invite community feedback.

Webinars

The project team will organize a series of webinars throughout the project duration to 1) advocate for FAIR practice, 2) communicate project efforts and progress, 3) provide training for researchers, 4) showcase project outputs and share system integration experience. We will record selected sessions to publish on the DataCite YouTube channel to serve as reference points for future use, ensuring the long-tail impact of the project outputs.

Workshops

The workshop format will be used extensively to gain insights from the stakeholders, experts, and the researchers community. Due to the constraints posed by the COVID pandemic, it is expected that most of the workshop will be hosted online, using Miro as the main facilitation platform. Information generated from the workshops will be archived on the Miro board for future reference.

Conferences

Both the project core team and partners will actively contribute to conferences in the domain of research data and neuroscience research, representing the project. We will take these opportunities to gain visibility, communicate outputs, and invite feedback from the communities. Some of the conferences we plan to attend include the Research Data Alliance plenary meetings, INCF Assembly, Sage Bionetworks annual assembly, NISO Plus, EuroCRIS and FORCE11 meetings.

Training and referential material

The FAIR Workflows adoption guide for researchers is one of the main training outputs defined in the project. This document will provide the practical know-how for the researchers in the consciousness research community, to clarify the concept of FAIR workflows and lower the barrier to adoption. We plan to use text, graphic, audio-visual mediums to ensure the effectiveness of the training. Once developed, it will be heavily used in subsequent communication activities and featured in all communication channels to maximize the effect of dissemination.

Project partners will create documentation outlining their technical integration details, as well as publications describing the implementation process and outcome, to provide research service platforms beyond the project with sufficient resources and reference to plan and implement their own integrations to join the effort in contributing to the FAIRification of research. We will coordinate with the partners to use templates when generating documentation for the project to ensure alignment and readability of the content.

Other materials generated in webinars, workshops and conferences, including slides, recordings, interview and survey data, will be curated and shared with project stakeholders on the DataCite YouTube channel and Zenodo Community,

Articles and publications

The main project outputs will also be described in the format of research articles, depending on the suitable use case, either directly publicly deposited on open repositories, or submitted for publication in an open access journal. By the end of the project, a minimum of 3 publications will be produced including the end-to-end workflow specification document, workflow adoption guide for researchers, and articles describing the implementation experience for future implementers to use as reference. Aside from that, we also plan to curate and publish technical documentation of system integrations as the project progresses.

Timeline

To maintain the visibility of the project, we will make sure at any point during the entire project duration communication is covered by one or more channels, targeting different stakeholder groups. The goal of communication will gradually shift from gaining feedback from the community to shape and improve the project efforts in the first year, to dissemination and promotion of project outputs, as well as providing training for adoption. The general outlook of the communication timeline is mapped to Table 3. The actual dates and format of communication activities may be different depending on circumstances.

	Year 1				Year 2				Year 3			
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4

Social media												
Webinars												
Publications												
Conferences												
Workshops												

Table 3. Timeline for the publication of communication outputs and public engagement activities

Metrics

We plan to use a range of engagement monitoring tools to track the effect and impact of the communication efforts outlined in this plan. We will rely on automated quantitative reports whenever possible, e.g. Twitter statistics, Zoom logs, etc., and employ active survey tools to gauge effectiveness of the messages and channels. The usage of the output and publications produced by the project will also be readily tracked using the PID Graph. Examples of the metrics are listed in Table 4.

A successfully carried out communication effort during the project will generate engagement on the various topics around building research workflows with FAIR compliance in mind; deliver the messages with clarity and persuasiveness; and provide sufficient documentation and resources for researchers to adopt and service providers to implement the workflows. It is essential to avoid generating confusion when communicating due to the multi-faceted nature of the project efforts, by failing to target the right stakeholder group, incorporate community feedback, or keep the communication consistent.

Goal	Method of Measure	When
Generate engagement during the project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Virtual event attendance analysis (Zoom report) Evaluation survey analysis (Google form, Zoom poll, Menti questionnaire) Engagement generated through social media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collect statistics across social media platforms every 6 months Post-webinar survey in Q3Y1, Q3Y2, and Q3y3
Bring the researcher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of inquiries from researchers regarding adoption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publication views and downloads tallied at

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community onboard with the adoption of FAIR workflows	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Number of adoption cases• Usage of researcher guideline (social media mentions, citations)	the end of the project <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Adoption case studies at the end of the project
Provide reliable resources for future implementers	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Usage of technical integration documentation (views, downloads)• Usage of open code for dashboard (fork/ star/ watch, number of issues etc.)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Documentation views and downloads tallied at the end of the project• Adoption case studies at the end of the project• Github engagement statistics by the end of the project

Table 4. Examples of project communication success metrics